

LnL trace

4e+06

6e+06

8e+06

1e+07

Generation

LnL trace

LnPr trace

LnPr trace

TL.all. trace

TL.all. trace

8

10

12

14

TL.all.

m.1. trace

m.1. trace

m.2. trace

m.2. trace

m.3. trace

m.3. trace

m.4. trace

infile.nex.run1.t (ESS=3824)

infile.nex.run2.t (ESS=4582)

infile.nex.run3.t (ESS=4421)

infile.nex.run4.t (ESS=4000)

4e+06

6e+06

8e+06

1e+07

Generation

m.4.

m.4. trace

m.5. trace

m.5. trace

m.6. trace

m.6. trace

m.7. trace

m.7. trace

m.8. trace

m.8. trace

m.9. trace

infile.nex.run1.t (ESS=3675)

1.8
1.4
1.0

infile.nex.run2.t (ESS=3738)

1.8
1.4
1.0

infile.nex.run3.t (ESS=3732)

1.8
1.4
1.0

infile.nex.run4.t (ESS=3549)

1.8
1.4
1.0

4e+06

6e+06

8e+06

1e+07

Generation

m.9.

m.9. trace

1.0

1.4

1.8

2.2

m.9.

m.10. trace

m.10. trace

m.11. trace

m.11. trace

m.12. trace

m.12. trace

m.13. trace

m.13. trace

m.14. trace

m.14. trace

m.15. trace

infile.nex.run1.t (ESS=3174)

9

6

3

infile.nex.run2.t (ESS=2432)

9

6

3

infile.nex.run3.t (ESS=2402)

9

6

3

infile.nex.run4.t (ESS=2653)

9

6

3

4e+06

6e+06

8e+06

1e+07

Generation

m.15.

m.15. trace

m.16. trace

m.16. trace

m.17. trace

infile.nex.run1.t (ESS=3789)

6
4
2

infile.nex.run2.t (ESS=3363)

6
4
2

infile.nex.run3.t (ESS=2834)

6
4
2

infile.nex.run4.t (ESS=3449)

6
4
2

4e+06

6e+06

8e+06

1e+07

Generation

m.17.

m.17. trace

m.18. trace

m.18. trace

m.19. trace

m.19. trace

Tree topology trace

Tree topology trace

infile.nex.run1.t (Approximate ESS = 2492)

infile.nex.run2.t (Approximate ESS = 2737)

infile.nex.run3.t (Approximate ESS = 2177)

infile.nex.run4.t (Approximate ESS = 2542)

40

80

120

160

Topological Distance of Tree from Focal Tree

infile.nex.run1.t

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

infile.nex.run2.t

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

infile.nex.run3.t

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

infile.nex.run4.t

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

LnL

LnPr

topological.distance

Topological autocorrelation plot

Sliding Window Split Frequencies for 20 clades

Sliding window Change in Split Frequencies

infile.nex.run1.t

infile.nex.run2.t

infile.nex.run3.t

infile.nex.run4.t

4e+06

6e+06

8e+06

1e+07

Generation

Cumulative Split Frequencies for 20 clades

Cumulative Change in Split Frequencies

Tree space heatmap for 100 trees

Tree space for 100 trees

Average Standard Deviation of Split Frequencies

Split frequency comparisons

infile.nex.run3.t

infile.nex.run1.t

infile.nex.run4.t

infile.nex.run2.t

0.0000

0.0004

0.0008

0.0012

Pairwise ASDSF

